
IN THE DISCIPLINE OF SOLO SINGING, THE PLACE OF THE GRAND CHOIR

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Abstract.

Today, when it comes to the prospect of a national singing school, it is our most important task to study and restore our great spiritual value, our musical heritage, in the educational system.

Key words.

"Traditional and folk singing", "Basics of status", "Traditional singing", "Classical singing".

Because in the words of Al-Kindi, a great philosopher of the 9th century, "Learning the heritage of ancestors is a life that gives life to the minds of generations." Currently, in all higher education institutions where there is a music education, subjects such as "Traditional and folk singing", "Fundamentals of status", "Traditional singing", "Classical singing" are taught. The students are given practical and theoretical knowledge on the management of folk songs, classical singing, big singing and songs, which are the precious heritage of the Uzbek people. At the Department of National Singing of the Institute of Arts and Culture of Uzbekistan, students conduct group practical exercises on the subject of "Ashulachilar ensemble" (Traditional singing). The decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures for the further development of the Uzbek national makom art" signed on November 17, 2017 is a high example of the attention paid to the performance of makom, which is considered our traditional art.

In this decision, "At the same time, the wide possibilities of status art are not being used enough to realize our national identity, to develop our culture in all aspects, to educate our people, first of all, our young generation in the spirit of high human feelings, to form their aesthetic taste and thinking. In this direction, in-depth scientific-theoretical research, creation of educational and methodical

literature, promotion of the art of maqam in our country and abroad through radio-television, mass media, internet network, maqam teachers, field scientists and the work of materially and morally supporting the activities of specialists, talented and promising young performers has been neglected.

Big song, patnusaki (patnis) song is a traditional Uzbek song, unique to the Fargona Valley. Usually, 2-5 breaths are sung by the singer (hafiz) without musical accompaniment (holding a tray or plate in his hands). It is often performed with high pitches and wide breaths, and is distinguished by its own complex performance style. The big song consists of ancient ritual and work songs, laments, folk songs, women's songs, and ghazals with aruz weight. was created on the basis of reading styles. Big song is usually sung at large gatherings, parties and weddings. Along with lyrical and instructive ghazals, religious and mystical poems were also sung in his past samples. The ghazals of Navoi, Lutfiy, Mashrab, Khazini, Muqimi, Furqat, Zavqi, Miskin and others have a special place in the genre of big song.

Among the people are "Friends" (Navoiy), "Kop erdi", "Yolgiz", "I'm lost" (Muqimiy), "Oh who, rahm aylamas" (Furqat), "Bir kelsun", "Hey, dear soul" (Miskin). as Big chants are common. The poems of Habibiy, Chustiy, Kamtar, Charkhi, Sabir Abdulla, Akmal Polat, Vasit Sadulla, Nasimiy, Erkin Vahidov, Otkir Rashid and others are also performed with love in the big choir.

Badiha style is widely used in the performance of the big song. This ensures that the speech and melodic structures in it are perfectly and organically connected to each other, enriches the song with colorful musical decorations, and leads to the use of various climaxes. A senior choral performer should have a wide range, loud voice and skill, having gone through the traditional "master-disciple" school, relying on the laws of poetry and performance traditions. Hafiz usually perform each of the beginning verses of the verse in turn, and the last verses in accompaniment. In the 2nd half of the 20th century, new musical-instrumental ways of Katta ashula, types intended for a solo hafiz, appeared. In these examples, the musical ensemble played the role of a harmonist, and the free style of performance was preserved. This style of the big song was created by Jorakhan Sultanov ("Oh dear soul", "Ohkim", "Topmadim", "Guluzorim kani", "Mehnat akhli", "Uzbekistan" and others). Some branches of maqom ("Bayot", "Chorgoh", "Ushshok") are also sung in the style of Katta ashula ("wild maqom") (for example, "Yovvoyi Ushshok", "Patnusaki Chorgoh", "Likobi Bayot" and others). Skilled musicians created instrumental tracks (flute, trumpet, bell) of Katta Ashula. In the course of the development, schools of large singing performance (Ko'kan,

Margilon, Tashkent, Namangan - Andijan) were formed. Erkagori Karimov, Sherkozi Boykoziyev, Haydarali Hikmatov, Melikozi Yusupov, Otimboy Sarimsokov, Turdiali Ergashev, Otamirza Abdurahmonov (Kokan), Mamatbuva Satorov, Jorakhan Sultanov, Ma'murjon Uzokov, Boltaboy Rajabov, Ibrahim Ishakov, Musajon Orifjanov (Margilon), Arif Alimahsumov, Artikkhoja. Imamkhoyayev, Akbar Haydarov, Eshmat Haydarov, Ochilkhan Otakhonov (Tashkent), Fattakhkan Mamadaliyev, Odiljon Yusupov, Zhorakhon Yusupov (Andijan), Hamrokulqori Torakulov (Beshariq), Rasulqori Mamadaliyev (Buvayda), Salijon Hashimov (Kuvayda) and others gained fame as a performer of the Great Choir. Halima Nosirova, Munojot Yolchiyeva, Ismail and Israil Vahobov, Mahmud Tojiboyev, Mahmud Yoldoshev also skillfully perform the Great Choir.

Since 1984, competitions of senior singers (Margilon, 1984; Tashkent, 1987; Kokhan, 1991; Shahrisabz, 1994) have been held in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The ways of performing the big song have been mastered in traditional schools of skill (Baliqchi, Buvayda) and music schools (Fergana State Academy of Arts, State Conservatory of Uzbekistan). In 2001, the 1st Republican competition of professional senior choir performers and scientific-practical (Tashkent, Andijan) conferences were held in Andijan. Great composer (F. Sodikov, "Uzbekistan", "Toy Mubarak"; M. Murtozoyev, "Soginish" and others) and composers (V. Uspensky, "Lyric Poem"; M. Tajiyev, 3rd symphony; M. Bafoyev, a concert for the orchestra of folk instruments; B. Umidjonov, "Chorgoh" for a cappella) is feeding the creations.

A choral track that occupies a central place in the heritage of classical Uzbek music, intended for a solo singer or a group of singers. It mainly occurs on the ground of ghazals and poems in a lyrical spirit. Chants are performed with or without music (dora, dutor, tanbur), ensemble. Ashula differs from the song genre, which occupies a large place in Uzbek musical folklore, by the breadth of the melody range, the development of form, and the depth of the theme and content. In the artistic content of Ashula, finger-weight poems are used, while aruz-weight ghazals and poetic forms take the main place. Consequently, the internal structure of the song is also different. While songs based on finger weight are more in the form of "band-chorus", the structure of songs based on ghazals is relatively complex and developed.

Usually, the melody of such songs starts from the lower notes, develops in the middle and upper notes, and then ends in the first sustained sound. Most songs have their own climaxes. The history of the Ashula genre goes back to the distant past: most of them are the product of the work of professional musicians (composer-hafiz), and due to the fact that they have come down to us orally, a

number of Ashulas have many variants. The most developed and perfect forms of ashula were manifested in the prose (singing) ways of Bukhara and Khorezm maqams, and the maqam ways widespread in Tashkent and Fergana valleys in the big ashula genre. The spirit, character, and spiritual world of the Uzbek people found their mature and full-fledged artistic expression in hymns. The traditional singing performance school includes examples of classical singing and classical yallas, big singing, and maqam singing. Uzbek classical music includes classical songs and classical yallas. Each of them is distinguished by its own position, content, melodic system, form and performance styles. Ashula Mumtaz ashula is a large-scale folk song with a developed melody and form of a lyrical character. Ashula is one of the leading genres of classical music, distinguished by its melodic development, restrained lyrical or heavy character, exciting and painful content, wide range, considerable complexity of method and rhythm, and perfection of performance style. Eastern classical (such as Lutfi, Fuzuli, Alisher Navoi, Jami, Hazini, Mashrab, Muqimi, Furqat, Ogahi, Munis) and Uzbek (such as Chusti, Sabir Abdulla, Polat Momin, Erkin Vahidov, Kamtar, Normurod Narzullayev)) poets' ghazals, rubai, muhammas written in aruz weight are widely used in the song genre. Philosophical meaning, as well as romantic-lyrical and some admonitional content expressing pain, separation and sorrow, are more characteristic of the theme of the song.

In the hymn, the words and the melody are inextricably linked, and this situation constitutes the whole content and essence of the work. Because the general logical connection, weight, rhyme, melody, musicality in it arouses pleasure and excitement in the listener. Ashula as a genre is widely used in folklore and classical music, but it is distinguished by the texts of poems (folk words in folklore samples), melody development and performance styles, for example, "Tanovar" - "Black hair" in the folklore direction, "Sumbula", "Andi sendek" classic songs, "Adolat tanovar", "Yovvoyi tanovar" etc. (these are formed on the basis of one tone). Classical songs differ significantly from folk songs in the development of the musical text and relatively longer and wider range of melodic structures, the presence of a high climax. Their development process starts with income and develops gradually. Because of this, the work in the form of a song has a wide place in classical and compositional works, there are local versions of it, including folk song and muhammas in Bukhara, suvora and naqsh in Khorezm, song paths, big song, and wild song in the Fergana Valley. Classical songs on religious and preaching topics (Mashrab, Ahmad Yassavi, Ogahi, Khazini, Furqat, Huvaiddo, Makhtumquli) are called munojot, na't, qalandar, khanaqoi, hamd, manzuma. Such

songs are more complex and perfect in form and content and make up a significant part of our classical music.

Uzbek composers also created works based on the genre of classical music. These songs were performed by a soloist, accompanied by an instrumental ensemble. Classical songs such as "Tanovar", "Munojot", "Girya", "I'm lost", "Yolgiz", "Komating", "Kurd", "Ol Khabar", "Kuygay" (Yu. Rajabi), "I love you" (O. Hotamov), "Naylayin" (J. Sulstonov), "Hey, my face is on me" (F. Sodikov), "I say" (K. Jabborov), "With one job" (M. Murtazoyev), "Guluzorim" and "Sacrifice of death" (A. Abdurasulov), "When will happen" (M. Mirzayev) and others. The songs of the composers have a strong place in the repertoire of singers (professional and amateur). Major figures - K. Otaniyozov, J. Sulstonov, M. Uzokov, F. Mamadaliyev, R. Mamadaliyev, O. Khudoyshekurov, H. Boltayev, B. Dovidova, M. Tojiboyev, M. Yolchiyeva and others. There are also song series in Uzbek performance, including "Tanovar I-V", "Qalandar I-V", "Eshvoy-Eshvoy Kurd-Eshvoy Turkman", "Qalandari-Samandari", "Dilkhijoj-Sinakhijoj" and others. Yalla is a widespread song-dance genre with a romantic and lyrical content, performed by a soloist (singer or yallachi) accompanied by an instrumental ensemble. Classical yallas differ from folk yallas by a wide range of developed melody, attractive and playful character. Folk yallas are narrow in scope, with each stanza in its poetic text (mostly using folk poetry) and dance movements by a solo yalla, and the chorus accompanied by a band (more like a circle or dutor). It was mentioned in the playful character of the tune invites everyone to dance (yalla in folk language means "play song"), including folk songs such as "Yallama yorim", "Ho-ho yalla", "Kizgina" manes

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Among the experts, there are many who interpret this art as the art of loud singers who could not afford to buy musical words, which appeared in times of poverty. Some of our young artists are trying to call a big song a melody of a ghazal that is irregularly set to a melody and is sung in an irregular manner. It's a pity that many people take this mix as a big song. In fact, the big song is one of the genres of independent and mature Uzbek classical music, which is based on certain criteria and rules, and has been formed over centuries and carefully developed by master singers. Katta ashula was formed in the Fergana Valley and is a special direction of singing performance. At the same time, the big choir is a big school that has sharpened its performance practice, educated the skilled artists of its time, and perfectly combines a number of elements typical of the big choir in the art of choral performance. Already, its performance criteria require great talent, voice, perception, intelligence, creativity and skill from singers. It is very important to learn from masters who are connoisseurs of this elegant art, who know it well, who have mastered it perfectly, to promote it accordingly and to create new examples along the way. The most important thing is to educate modern performers, to educate a new generation of great singers, one of the urgent tasks. The art of great singing belongs to the series of unique sayings that have experienced certain historical processes, have left their mark in the life of the people, as well as the social, political and spiritual needs of the people. It is known that great songs were created in two ways in their creative ways. The first is the big songs that correspond to the status veils and are created on the basis of certain rules, that is, in musical terms, they are performed in the status veils. The second is large songs created by composers in different styles. In fact, the big song genre occupies a special place among the samples of our musical heritage. The reason we say this is that, due to the nature of the genre, it is related to the art of singing and is a perfect genre performed without musical notes.

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